

Challenges Faced by Nurses for Implementation of Nursing Process in Special Units at Teaching Hospital Jaffna

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ABSTRACT

The nursing process is a systematic problem-solving approach used to identify, prevent and treat actual or potential health problems and promote wellness. Implementation of nursing process will improve the patient care and decreases morbidity rate and hospital stay. In Teaching Hospital Jaffna, rate of morbidity and hospital stay are increased because of less consideration on application of nursing process. Therefore it was decided to conduct a study to assess the nurses' knowledge on nursing process and to identify the factors impact on implementation of nursing process in special units at Teaching Hospital, Jaffna. Descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 nurses working in special units at Teaching Hospital, Jaffna. Convenient sampling method was used. Data were collected by using structured self-administrated questionnaire. Data were analyzed in descriptive statistical method. Among the participants 63% were females; 60% were less than 30 years; 76% were Tamils; 64% were Hindus, 46% nurses had 3-6 years working experience; 31% of participants from Medical Intensive Care Unit (MICU). Results show that 17% of nurses had enough knowledge about nursing process. 88% and 69.8% of nurses reported that less time and workload are the major personnel barriers for implementing nursing process respectively. Institutional factors took the greatest part for lack of implementation of nursing process. Government must reemphasize on the provision of adequate resources to improve the practice of nursing process.

Key words: Challenges, Factors, Nurses, Nursing process, Teaching Hospital.

INTRODUCTION

The nursing process is a systematic problem-solving approach used to identify, prevent and treat actual or potential health problems and promote wellness. The nursing process is widely accepted method and has been suggested as a scientific method to guide procedures and quality nursing care. [1] It has five steps: assessment, diagnosis, planning, implementation and evaluation. Nursing process is an essential part of the nursing care plan. International Council of Nursing (ICN) and the American Joint Commission on Accreditation of Hospital Nursing Service Standards highly recommended that nursing process should be used in nursing documentation and promoted the use of the nursing process in nursing care. [2] Nursing involves assisting others with basic human needs using a holistic approach and the patient is defined as someone who needs care. The majority of nurses have knowledge on nursing process but they don't apply in practice. [3] It is difficult to bring significant improvement in nursing care if nurses do not use nursing process to assess, plan, implement and evaluate clinical condition of the client. More ever, malpractice of nursing process will affect quality of nursing care as a result of different factors. [4] Implementation of the nursing process leads to improved quality of care and stimulates the construction of theoretical and scientific knowledge based on the best clinical practice. [5] Due to this, quality of care will improve and decreases morbidity rate and hospital stay.

Furthermore, nurse's positive attitude, lack of sufficient time, lack of authority support, disorganized working environment, and harassing co-workers were the challenges in developing countries. [6] In Teaching Hospital, Jaffna morbidity rate and hospital stay were increased. Therefore it was decided to conduct a study to assess the nurses' knowledge on nursing process and to identify the factors impact on implementation of nursing process in special units at Teaching Hospital, Jaffna.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 nurses working in special units at Teaching Hospital, Jaffna. Convenient sampling method was used. Nurses who were willing to participate and available during the study period were included as respondents and who were on leave were excluded from the study. Data were collected by using structured self-administrated questionnaire which included questions regarding socio-demographic details, nurses' knowledge on nursing process, personal factors & institutional factors that influence to implement the nursing process. The questionnaire was generated by conceptual frame works that results from review of literatures, experts' opinions and personal observations. The content validity of questionnaire was assured by referring to subject experts, relevant books and by searching web

engines. Reliability and readability of questionnaire was assured by a pre-test. Ethical clearance was obtained from Ethics Review Committee of Faculty of Medicine, Jaffna. Pilot study was carried out among 5 nurses from Base Hospital, Tellipalai. Permission to conduct this study was obtained from obtained from Matron, Base Hospital, Thellipalai and from Director, Teaching Hospital, Jaffna. Director, Teaching Hospital, Jaffna through Matron. Data were analyzed by using SPSS19 statistical software in descriptive statistical method to assess the knowledge regarding nursing process and to identify the factors impact on practicing nursing process.

RESULTS

Among the participants 63% were females; 60% were under the age group of less than 30 years; 76% were Tamils; 64% were Hindus, 46% nurses had 3-6 years working experience; 31% of participants from MICU. Figure 1 describes the knowledge and awareness regarding nursing process. This finding indicates that only 17% of nurses had enough knowledge about nursing process. Only 7% of nurses were aware about the first step in nursing process. 27% and 35% of nurses understood activities during planning phases and nurses' role during implementation phase in nursing process respectively. Only 3% of nurses know about nurse's performance for evaluation in nursing process.

Figure 1: Knowledge and awareness regarding nursing process

While considering the personal factors influencing in application of nursing process 52% of participants strongly agreed that positive attitude is important for the practice of nursing process. 58% of nurses strongly agreed that adequate working experience also influencing the implementation of nursing process. 88%, 69.8% nurses reported that not enough time and workload are the barriers for implementing nursing process respectively. According to the current findings all participants reported that they were suffering from physical and mental stress, such as back pain, work load and time management problems which are influencing in practicing nursing process.

In Teaching Hospital, Jaffna most of the nurses have lack of theoretical knowledge regarding nursing process. Shortages of nursing staff, unavailability of materials for documentation are most common barriers for application of nursing process. 73%, 42%, 48% of participants reported that nurses' involvement is needed, superiors supports is need and ward managers' need to have positive concept about nursing process for the application of nursing process respectively

DISCUSSION

Findings of this study indicate that only 17% of nurses had enough knowledge about nursing process. Similar results were found in another study. [1] Only 7% of nurses aware about the first step in nursing process. Contrast finding was there in another study, [5] 27% and 35% of nurses understood activities during planning phases and nurses' role during implementation phase in nursing process respectively. Similar results were found in another study. [6]

52% of participants strongly agreed that positive attitude is an important personal factor for the practice of nursing process. Similar findings are available in a study which was done in Ethiopia. [1] Many nurses reported that not enough time and workload are the barriers for implementing

nursing process, similar findings available in a study, done in bad zone hospitals of South East Ethiopia. [7-8] All participants in current study reported that they were suffering from physical and mental stress, which are influencing in practicing nursing process. Similar findings are available in a study, done in Ethiopia. [1]

In Teaching Hospital, Jaffna most of the nurses have lack of theoretical knowledge regarding nursing process. Meanwhile shortage of nursing staff, unavailability of materials for documentation; Similarly a study done in Brazil showed that lack of time, high patient turnover and lack of administrative support were the factors limited the ability of nurses to implement the nursing process in their daily practice. [9]

CONCLUSION

Health care delivery system of Sri Lanka is aiming to offer the highest possible quality of health care services to many people. Nurses should use nursing process to make their work visible and valuable to improve the quality of care. Hence, implementation of nursing process is affected by various factors, if nurses have adequate knowledge about implementation of nursing process, they can apply easily. Institutional factors took the greatest part for lack of implementation of nursing process.

Alleviating the barriers based on the personal and institutional factors can increase the application of nursing process in health care service. From the findings of this study it is recommended that nurses and nurse educators should update their knowledge on nursing process in theoretical aspect as well as practical aspects. Government must reemphasize on the provision of adequate resources such as materials, and nursing staff to health institutions.

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